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Vitrification preserves follicular transcriptomic dynamics during ex vivo ovulation

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Abstract:	<p>Vitrification of immature follicles is an emerging approach for studying ovarian biology, toxicology, fertility preservation, and female contraception. We previously used a 3D encapsulated in vitro follicle growth (eIVFG) model to demonstrate that murine follicles using a closed vitrification system exhibit normal follicle development, hormone secretion, and ovulation, and preserve follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH)-stimulated follicular transcriptome. Here, we investigated whether the molecular signatures of ovulation, another gonadotropin-dependent follicular event, are conserved in vitrified follicles. Preovulatory follicles grown from fresh or vitrified follicles in eIVFG were treated with human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) to trigger ovulation. Follicles were collected at 0, 1, 4, and 8-hour for single-follicle RNA sequencing. Principal component analysis showed that fresh and vitrified follicles were separated into distinct clusters by time, but fresh and vitrified follicles at the same time points largely overlapped. Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG analysis using identified differentially expressed genes (DEGs) revealed a few enriched GO terms and signaling pathways, which may affect molecular aspects of ovulation and/or subsequent luteinization. Pearson's correlation analysis showed the fold changes of most DEGs at 1, 4, or 8-hour VS. 0-hour were highly correlated between fresh and vitrified follicles. Moreover, both the expression</p>

	levels and temporal patterns of well-established ovulatory genes were consistent between fresh and vitrified follicles. Taken together, our study demonstrates that the closed vitrification system preserves follicular transcriptomic dynamics during ex vivo ovulation, enabling a high-quality follicle biobank for fertility preservation, endangered species conservation, and studies of ovulation biology, anovulatory disease, toxicology, and novel contraceptive development.
Additional Information:	
Question	Response

1 *Title*

2 **Vitrification preserves follicular transcriptomic dynamics during ex vivo ovulation**

3

4 *Short title*

5 **Vitrification preserves ovulatory transcriptome**

6

7 *Keywords*

8 Vitrification, ovulation, single-follicle RNA sequencing

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42 **Abstract**

43 Vitrification of immature follicles is an emerging approach for studying ovarian biology,
44 toxicology, fertility preservation, and female contraception. We previously used a 3D
45 encapsulated *in vitro* follicle growth (eIVFG) model to demonstrate that cryopreserved
46 follicles using a closed vitrification system exhibit normal follicle development, hormone
47 secretion, and ovulation, and vitrified follicles preserve follicle-stimulating hormone
48 (FSH)-stimulated follicular transcriptome. Here, we investigated whether the molecular
49 signatures of ovulation, another gonadotropin-dependent follicular event, are conserved
50 in vitrified follicles. Preovulatory follicles grown from fresh or vitrified immature follicles in
51 eIVFG were treated with human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) to trigger ovulation.
52 Follicles were collected at 0, 1, 4, and 8-hour for single-follicle RNA sequencing. Principal
53 component analysis showed that fresh and vitrified follicles were separated into distinct
54 clusters by post-hCG hours, but fresh and vitrified follicles at the same time points largely
55 overlapped. Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG analysis using identified differentially
56 expressed genes (DEGs) revealed a few enriched GO terms and signaling pathways,
57 which may affect molecular aspects of ovulation and/or subsequent luteinization.
58 Pearson's correlation analysis showed that the fold changes of most DEGs at 1, 4, or 8-
59 hour VS. 0-hour were highly correlated between fresh and vitrified follicles. Moreover,
60 both the expression levels and temporal patterns of well-established ovulatory genes
61 were highly consistent between fresh and vitrified follicles. Taken together, our study
62 demonstrates that the closed vitrification system preserves follicular transcriptomic
63 dynamics during *ex vivo* ovulation, enabling a high-quality follicle biobank for fertility

64 preservation, endangered species conservation, and studies of ovulation biology,
65 anovulatory disease, toxicology, and novel contraceptive development.

66

67 Dear Editor,

68 Vitrification is an emerging cryopreservation approach for storing cells or tissues at ultra-
69 low temperatures over an extended period of time. Compared to traditional slow-freezing,
70 vitrification is more cost-effective due to the simple and short process. Vitrification is
71 widely used in assisted reproductive technology (ART) to cryopreserve gametes,
72 embryos, or gonad tissues for fertility preservation and infertility treatment. We previously
73 demonstrated that a closed vitrification system preserves murine follicle viability, and
74 vitrified follicles exhibited comparable functions to fresh follicles in an *in vitro* 3D
75 encapsulated follicle growth (eIVFG) system, including follicle maturation, hormone
76 secretion, ovulation, and resumption of oocyte meiosis [1]. Our recent study further
77 demonstrated the faithful preservation of molecular signatures of vitrified murine follicles
78 during follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH)-stimulated maturation [2]. However, it is
79 unknown whether ovulation, another crucial gonadotropin-dependent follicular event, and
80 the involved ovulatory genes and signaling are well conserved in vitrified follicles.

81

82 Ovulation is a complex dynamic process by which a surge of the luteinizing hormone (LH)
83 from the anterior pituitary stimulates a fully grown preovulatory follicle to release a
84 fertilizable oocyte. LH binds to its surface receptor in mural granulosa cells and theca
85 cells of a preovulatory follicle, and activates a series of signaling molecules to drive key
86 ovulatory events, including follicle rupture, cumulus cell expansion, and resumption of

87 oocyte meiosis I. We have recently demonstrated that the eIVFG-based *ex vivo* ovulation
88 not only morphologically recapitulates these key ovulatory events but also conserves the
89 ovulatory gene regulatory pathways, such as those related to epidermal growth factor
90 receptor (EGFR), extracellular signal-regulated kinase 1/2 (ERK1/2), progesterone
91 receptor, inflammation, and proteolysis [3]. Herein, we further determine whether
92 vitrification of immature follicles preserves the ovulation potential at molecular levels when
93 follicles mature to the preovulatory stage in eIVFG.

94

95 Multi-layered secondary follicles isolated from 16-day-old CD-1 mouse ovaries were
96 vitrified as we previously described [1, 2, 4]. With fresh follicles as the control, vitrified
97 follicles were warmed and cultured for 8 days in eIVFG [5, 6]. Vitrified and fresh follicles
98 were grown to preovulatory stage and were freed from alginate encapsulation and treated
99 with 1.5 IU/mL human chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) to induce ovulation *ex vivo* [3].
100 Follicles were collected at 0, 1, 4, and 8-hour post-hCG for single-follicle RNA sequencing
101 (RNA-seq, GEO number: GSE227091) using an optimized SMART-seq2 protocol [7].
102 Fastq files were generated using bcl2fastq and imported into the Partek Flow software.
103 Reads were aligned to the whole mouse genome assembly-mm10 using the HISAT 2
104 align, quantified by Ensembl Transcripts release 99 using the Partek EM algorithm, and
105 normalized using the Transcripts Per Million (TPM) method, and differential gene
106 expression analysis was performed using the DESeq2(R). Principal component analysis
107 (PCA) showed distinct follicle separation across post-hCG time points, but separation was
108 not seen between fresh and vitrified follicles at each time (Fig. 1A). The volcano plots in
109 Suppl. Fig. 1 and Suppl. Table 1 showed all identified differentially expressed genes

110 (DEGs) with fold change >2 or <0.5 and false discovery rate (FDR) adjusted p -value $<$
111 0.05 between vitrified and fresh follicles at each time points. There were 52, 130, 30, and
112 476 DEGs at 0, 1, 4, and 8-hour post-hCG, respectively. Gene Ontology (GO) and KEGG
113 pathway analysis over these DEGs using the functional enrichment tool WebGestalt [8]
114 revealed that none or a few GO terms and signaling pathways were enriched at 0, 1, and
115 4-hour (Suppl. Table 2). At 8-hour, DEGs were primarily associated with Cell cycle,
116 GTPase binding, and AMPK signaling, etc. Whether these DEGs along with enriched GO
117 terms and signaling pathways after vitrification are not sufficient to affect ovulation at the
118 morphological and hormonal levels or they affect molecular events of ovulation and/or
119 subsequent luteinization requires further investigations.

120

121 We further calculated different sets of DEGs at 1, 4, and 8-hour VS. 0-hour in fresh or
122 vitrified follicles and examined correlations of DEGs between fresh and vitrified follicles
123 at each time point. The fold changes of most DEGs at each time points were highly
124 correlated between fresh and vitrified follicles with Pearson's correlation coefficients (R)
125 of 0.9443, 0.9589, and 0.9307 at 1, 4, and 8-hour, respectively (Fig. 1B). The majority of
126 LH target genes are highly induced and peak in follicular cells at 4 hours in both *in vivo*
127 and *in vitro* ovulation models [3, 9]. We next selected the top 100 up-regulated ovulatory
128 genes at 4-hour post-hCG VS. 0-hour in fresh follicles and compared the temporal log-
129 transformed expression patterns of these 100 genes at all four post-hCG time points. Both
130 the expression levels and temporal patterns of these 100 genes were highly consistent
131 between fresh and vitrified follicles, including many genes that have been reported to
132 critically regulate ovulation (Fig. 1C and Supplemental Table 3). In Fig. 1D, we provided

133 a more detailed illustration of the consistent transcriptional dynamics of several well-
134 established ovulatory genes, including genes involved in the EGF signaling (*Areg*),
135 cumulus cell expansion (*Has2*), follicle rupture (*Pgr*), inflammation (*Ptgs2*), luteinization
136 (*Star*), and proteolysis (*Plau*).

137
138 In summary, these results demonstrate that our closed vitrification system preserves
139 follicular transcriptomic dynamics during *ex vivo* ovulation. Together with our previous
140 findings that vitrification preserves FSH-stimulated follicle maturation [1, 2], the integration
141 of vitrification of immature follicles and eIVFG has a great potential to serve as an
142 additional fertility preservation approach for young cancer patients and endangered
143 species. Moreover, follicle vitrification enables a high-quality/content ovarian follicle
144 biobank, which can greatly improve the throughput of eIVFG for studying ovulation
145 biology, anovulatory disease, toxicology, and novel contraceptive development targeting
146 ovulation. Along with follicle maturation, the follicle-enclosed oocyte produces and
147 accumulates maternal mRNAs, proteins, and organelles to acquire meiotic and
148 developmental competence for subsequent fertilization and early embryogenesis. This
149 process, termed oogenesis, largely relies on the bidirectional communications between
150 the oocyte and surrounding follicular somatic cells [10]. In future studies, we will
151 determine whether our closed vitrification system preserves oogenesis.

152

153 **Data availability**

154 All associated RNA-seq data including fastq files and processed raw counts can be found at the
155 Gene Expression Omnibus (GSE227091).

156

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163 Attribution 4.0 Generic License has already been assigned to the Author Accepted
164 Manuscript version that might arise from this submission.

165

166 **Conflict of interest**

167 A. K. S. reports compensation for consulting and/or SAB membership from Honeycomb
168 Biotechnologies, Cellarity, FL86, Senda Biosciences, IntrECate Therapeutics, Relation
169 Therapeutics, and Dahlia Biosciences. B. A. G. reports compensation for consulting for
170 FL82. M. B. Z. is a consultant for Oviva Therapeutics and Gaia Life. Other co-authors
171 declare no conflict of interest.

172

173 **Author Contributions**

174 J. Zhang, D. D. Russo, Y. Wang, and B. A. Goods contributed to the experimental design,
175 data collection and analysis, and manuscript writing; Q. Zhang and A. K. Shalek
176 contributed to the experimental design and manuscript writing; M. B. Zelinski contributed
177 to the vitrification protocol development and manuscript writing; S. Xiao conceived the

178 project, designed experiments, interpreted data, wrote the manuscript, and provided final
179 approval of the manuscript.

180

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205

206 **Figure Legend**

207 **Figure 1.** Comparison of the follicular transcriptomes during ovulation between fresh and
208 vitrified follicles using single-follicle RNA-seq. (A) PCA of the first two principal
209 components between fresh and vitrified follicles at different time points post-hCG. Ellipses
210 represent 95% confidence intervals. n=3-18 follicles in each group. (B) Pearson's
211 correlation analysis of DEGs for fresh and vitrified follicles at 1, 4, and 8-hour post hCG,
212 respectively. (C) mRNA expression levels (Log₂ (TPM+1)) at all four time points post-
213 hCG for the top 100 up-regulated genes identified at 4-hour post-hCG. (D) mRNA

214 expression levels ($\text{Log}_2(\text{TPM}+1)$) of representative ovulatory genes in fresh (F) and
215 vitrified (V) follicles at different time points post-hCG.

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